

Glyphosate: EFSA and Experts from EU Member States Confirm Scientific Assessment of German Authorities

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The EU approval process for glyphosate as active substance in plant protection products is meanwhile in the political decision-making phase in the area of risk management. The European Food Safety Authority (EFSA) published its conclusion on the peer review of glyphosate on 12 November 2015 (www.efsa.europa.eu). On 30 October 2015, the European Food Safety Authority (EFSA) submitted its Conclusion to the European Commission and the member states of the European Union. This completes the scientific assessment process for the active substance. The risk management authorities will review the report submitted by EFSA and then decide whether to renew the approval for the use of glyphosate as an active substance in pesticides.

One of the sources for the EFSA Conclusion is the Renewal Assessment Report (RAR) from Germany, including its revisions and the addendum on the assessment of the IARC monograph. Within the framework of the public and expert consultation process on glyphosate organised by EFSA, comments were submitted from the sectors of the general public, science, political decision-makers, industry and non-governmental organisations. The assessments in the RAR on health-related and environmentally relevant risks have been thoroughly reviewed, commented and then discussed in depth by EFSA and experts from the competent authorities of the member states. In the EFSA Conclusion, the majority of European experts also confirm the health assessment of the Federal Institute for Risk Assessment (BfR), stating that no carcinogenic, mutagenic or developmental toxic effects are to be expected in humans from the appropriate use of glyphosate in agricultural operations.

The BfR strongly recommends that discussions regarding scientific studies be conducted on a scientific level, and of course, when necessary also in a controversial manner. The scientific publication process is an integral part of scientific work. Hypotheses or commentaries on studies can only be included in the process of scientific discourse if they have been published and if the conclusions drawn are transparent and can be logically analysed. As the scientific assessment of the active substance glyphosate has been completed, the political decision-makers can now reach a decision based on the scientific assessment of glyphosate.

Reference to the EFSA publications on the EFSA website

Glyphosate: EFSA updates toxicological profile

<http://www.efsa.europa.eu/en/press/news/151112>

EFSA explains risk assessment: Glyphosate

http://www.efsa.europa.eu/sites/default/files/corporate_publications/files/efsaexplainsglyphosate151112en_1.pdf

Conclusion on the peer review of the pesticide risk assessment of the active substance glyphosate

http://www.efsa.europa.eu/sites/default/files/scientific_output/files/main_documents/4302.pdf